

REPORT

The XXXV International Conference on Multivariate Statistical Analysis, 7–9 November 2016, Łódź, Poland

The 35th edition of the International Conference on Multivariate Statistical Analysis was held in Łódź, Poland, on November 7-9, 2016. The MSA 2016 conference was organized by the Department of Statistical Methods of the University of Lodz, the Institute of Statistics and Demography of the University of Lodz, the Polish Statistical Association and the Committee on Statistics and Econometrics of Polish Academy of Sciences. The Mayor of the City of Łódź, Hanna Zdanowska, took the honorary patronage of the Multivariate Statistical Analysis MSA 2016 conference. Its organization was financially supported by the National Bank of Poland, the Polish Academy of Sciences and StatSoft Polska Sp. z o.o. The Organizing Committee was headed by Professor Czesław Domański. The scientific secretaries included Piotr Szczepocki, M.Sc. and Jacek Białek, Assistant Professor from the Department of Statistical Methods of the University of Lodz.

As all previous Multivariate Statistical Analysis conferences, the 2016 edition was aimed at creating the opportunity for scientists and practitioners of statistics to present and discuss the latest theoretical achievements in the field of the multivariate statistical analysis, its practical aspects and applications. The scientific programme covered various statistical problems, including multivariate estimation methods, statistical tests, non-parametric inference, discrimination analysis, Monte Carlo analysis, Bayesian inference, application of statistical methods in finance and economy, especially methods used in capital market and risk management. The range of topics also included the design of experiments and survey sampling methodology, mainly for the social science purposes.

The conference was attended by 78 participants from main academic centres in Poland (Białystok, Katowice, Kraków, Olsztyn, Opole, Poznań, Rzeszów, Szczecin, Toruń, Warszawa and Wrocław) and from abroad (Italy). In 17 sessions 64 papers were presented, including 2 invited lectures.

The conference was opened by the Head of the Organizing Committee, Professor Czesław Domański. The subsequent speakers at the conference opening included Dominik Rozkrut, the Head of Central Statistical Office of Poland and Assistant Professor Michał Przybyliński, the Deputy Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Sociology of the University of Lodz.

After the opening ceremony, all participants had the opportunity to attend the invited lecture by Professor Józef Pociecha (Cracow University of Economics) *Statistics Of Poland – The First Yearbook Of Polish Lands*. The second invited lecture was presented by Professor Włodzimierz Okrasa (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw) and was titled *The Quality Of Life and The Surroundings*.

Among regular conference sessions, the historical plenary session was held, chaired by Professor Włodzimierz Okrasa (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw), and dedicated to eminent Polish scientists. Professor Czesław Domański (University of Lodz) presented statistical threads in the work of Jan Śniadecki. Professor Mirosław Krzyśko (Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań) recalled his memories of Mikołaj Olekiewicz. Professor Jan Kordos (Warsaw Management University) presented the work of Jan Buga.

Other sessions were chaired respectively by:

SESSION II	Professor Danuta Strahl (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION III A	Professor Małgorzata Markowska (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION III B	Professor Andrzej Dudek (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION IV A	Professor Grzegorz Kończak (University of Economics in Katowice)
SESSION IV B	Professor Grażyna Trzpiot (University of Economics in Katowice)
SESSION V	Professor Bronisław Ceranka (Poznań University of Life Sciences)
SESSION VI A	Professor Grażyna Dehnel (Poznań University of Economics)
SESSION VI B	Professor Tadeusz Bednarski (University of Wrocław)
SESSION VII A	Professor Wojciech Zieliński (Warsaw University of Life Sciences)
SESSION VII B	Professor Jerzy Korzeniewski (University of Łódź)
SESSION VIII A	Professor Alina Jędrzejczak (University of Łódź)
SESSION VIII B	Professor Iwona Markowicz (University of Szczecin)
SESSION IX A	Professor Janusz Wywiół (University of Economics in Katowice)
SESSION IX B	Professor Marek Walesiak (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION X	Professor Andrzej Sokołowski (Cracow University of Economics)
SESSION XI	Professor Józef Dziechciarz (Wrocław University of Economics)

The MSA 2016 conference was closed by the Chairman of the Organizing Committee, Professor Czesław Domański, who summarized the Conference and thanked all the guests, conference partners and sponsors.

The next edition of Multivariate Statistical Analysis Conference MSA 2017 is planned on November 6-8, 2017 and will be held in Łódź, Poland. The Chairman of the Organizing Committee, Professor Czesław Domański, informed that this will be the 36th edition of the conference and kindly invited all interested scientists, researchers and students to participate.

Prepared by:

Piotr Szczepocki

Department of Statistical Methods, University of Łódź.

Jacek Białek

Department of Statistical Methods, University of Łódź